

Policy Brief - Enhancing National Legal Frameworks to Tackle Deepfakes in India

Author: Chaithra Jayanth

Email: jchaithra@gmail.com

Data Availability Statement: The policy brief presented here is based on literature reviews, white papers, journals and newspaper articles. Not much research has been done in India to address deepfakes and analyse its impact, but there are certain discussions in the journals, think tanks and newspaper articles which speak about the effect of deepfakes in India and also suggest changes.

Executive Summary

The rise of deepfake technology is attributed to the vast connectivity on social media platforms. The novelty of deepfake technology makes it a challenge for policy-makers to understand its intricacies and draft a strong legal framework to mitigate its negative impact on the society and protect personal data. According to Nema, P., plethora of personal data such as images and videos available on the internet and social media platforms and accessible deepfake algorithms have resulted in the increased use of deepfakes by miscreants (2021).

This policy brief suggests enhancing the Indian legal framework to address deepfakes to ameliorate potential damages and discusses the following key points:

- Accessibility of deepfake technology through consumer level applications and role of deepfake technology-providers in controlling its impact.
- Impact of deepfakes in the political sphere, its role in destabilising democratic processes and attack on the Government formed by law.
- Digital resurrection of the deceased with deepfakes and post-mortem privacy.
- High online presence of deepfake pornography and its rapid increase.

According to Paris, B. & Donovan, J, “Misuse of one’s likeness is expensive to address through the legal system” (Deepfakes and Cheap Fakes, 2019). The study by Nema states that, one of the biggest issues faced by many on online space is to identify and penalise miscreants and wrongdoers (2021). It is imperative to enhance India’s legal framework to tackle the negative impact of deepfake technology while preserving the positive implications of the technology.

Introduction

India is the largest democracy and is one of the largest consumers and producers of data per capita. Advancement in artificial intelligence has led to the generation of morphed audios and videos which look realistic. The emergence of synthetically generated and digitally manipulated media has significantly raised the concerns about its potential misuse leading to devastating effects on politics, individuals, organisations and the society at large. In response to these concerns, this policy-brief analyses the societal impacts of deepfakes and suggests enhancing the legal framework in India to tackle its impacts.

In Britt Paris and Joan Donovan’s work, “Deepfakes and Cheap Fakes, Data & Society”, they define deepfake as an audio-video manipulation through machine-learning to “hybridise or generate human bodies and faces (Paris, B. & Donovan, J., 2019). With social media, the proliferation of deepfake technology has increased as the morphed audios and videos can be spread at unprecedented speed. In India, the first landmark issue of usage of deepfake technology was in February 2020, during the Delhi Assembly polls. It was a morphed video of a prominent politician criticising his opponent candidate while in reality, he was talking of a completely different issue. The perfect lip-sync makes the misleading video seem realistic. Over the years, there has been an increase in the quantity and quality of deepfakes published on the internet which makes it a growing cause of concern for the government.

Deepfakes have a significant impact on the political sphere around the world. Today, consumer-level apps can be used to create deepfakes, there are algorithms that create moving faces with an image and it is possible to create full-body-faking and generate people as required which can be used in the clips of political rallies or fake rallies to show a politician’s

popularity (Mehra, n.d.). There are several instances of government-cover ups, smear campaigns which prove that deepfakes are powerful tools that destabilise the political system and without a way to counter its impact, there is a risk to the integrity of Indian democracy.

At a time when use of social media and messaging platforms are playing a major role in poisoning people's minds, deepfakes will add to the damages. It is possible that synthetically developed audio or video can be convincing enough to take the form of disinformation and one would find it difficult to differentiate between fact and fake news. This damages the popular belief that video and audio are reliable sources of information and can lead to erosion of trust, destabilise the country's economy, damage the judicial system and smear international relations. The spread of disinformation can be curbed with decisive measures and actions taken by the government by enhancing its legal framework (Mehra, n.d.-a).

According to Deepttrace, non-consensual deepfake pornography accounts for 96% of total online deepfake videos (Ajder, H. et al.,2019). According to the deepttrace reports, in 2018, there were about 134 million views across four major pornographic websites mostly targeting female celebrities (Ajder, H. et al.,2019). This suggests that there is a market for creating and hosting deepfake pornography. Pornography using deepfake is here to stay and this policy brief hopes to help stimulate discussions around the importance of protecting individuals and organisations from the effect of its trends and develop a range of countermeasures to tackle it.

According to Kohl, personal rights do not automatically expire upon death (Kohl, 2022). The advantages of producing high quality, low-budget imitations of people and has been used for both playful or malign purposes or is used to resurrect an eminent personality (Lees et al., 2021). But, the current legal framework in India does not clearly address the post-mortem publicity rights to preserve the rights of the deceased especially when their digital imitations are defamatory towards the deceased.

It is important to limit the risk of deepfakes while utilising its potential and to come up with a combination of measures by strengthening the legal framework and strengthening the Digital Protection Policies proposed by the Indian Government.

Research Overview

The policy brief presented here is based on literature reviews, white papers, journals and newspaper articles. Not much research has been done in India to address deepfakes and analyze its impact, but there are certain discussions in the journals, think tanks and newspaper articles which speak about the effect of deepfakes in India and also suggest changes.

Some countries have laws to regulate deepfake technologies. The DEEP FAKES Accountability Act, 2019, introduced in the United States of America, establishes the requirement to consider the need for a strong legal framework for dealing with new technologies and synthetic media and to contemporize the legal system to match it up with the present world. The DEEP FAKE Accountability Act establishes that the creators of deepfake materials are compelled to provide disclaimers and the software applications, which produce deepfakes are impelled to use watermarks and disclosures for the purpose of identification, failing which they are subjected to civil penalties (H.R.3230 – 116th Congress (2019-2020): DEEP FAKES Accountability Act, 2019).

The General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR), which is a European Data Protection Regulatory body set up to harmonise data privacy laws in all its member states across Europe, lays down certain general rules for processing personal data (General Data Protection

Regulation (GDPR) – Official Legal Text, 2022). According to GDPR, personal data is defined as information relating to an identified or identifiable natural person (General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) – Official Legal Text, 2022). To achieve high accuracy, the deepfake technology uses personal data to train the algorithms. The fragments of audios, videos or images can be used to trace back to the individuals. GDPR provides certain guidelines to protect the rights of individual's privacy and personal data. Article 35 of GDPR provides clear guidelines to perform the Data Protection Impact Assessment (DPIA) and provides certain legal grounds for personal data processing and for the creation and publishing of deepfake content. According to Article 6 and 7, which delineates the lawfulness of data processing conditions for consent, GDPR makes it clear that only legitimate interests and informed consent from the person being depicted will qualify to be published by the controller or the third-party (General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) – Official Legal Text, 2022).

Although the written regulations in both the above cases are strong, there are a few drawbacks. Firstly, the regulations are primarily concerned about protection of personal data, but do not critically address pornographic deepfakes. Secondly, while identifying a deepfake material through the watermarks or meta-data based markers could be a first step towards mitigating its potential negative impacts, the nature and scope of this measure remains unclear because, although illegal, removing the meta-data marker is easy. Thirdly, the policies do not delineate the post-mortem right of publicity. For instance, the deceased cannot file a defamation case because of the concept that a derogatory statement cannot harm the feelings of the deceased (Lees et al., 2021).

In India, the current discussions are focused on identifying deepfake materials and potentially eliminating them by tightening the laws around usage of social media platforms and encouraging organisations to take tougher actions against deepfakes (Tackling Deepfakes in European Policy, 2022). But, it is important to understand that technologies have both positive and negative implications. With the pace of technological developments, eliminating the usage and dissemination of deepfake materials proves to be a major challenge especially so with the existing detection tools. Efforts are being made to enhance the performance of these detection tools by companies like Google and Facebook, but since the law does not grow at the pace of technology, technology has always had an upper hand. It becomes pertinent to build a strong legal framework considering the regulations implemented in other countries, carefully studying the pros and cons and enhancing the existing laws in India to reduce the impact of the technology on the society at large.

Current Situation

Currently, India does not have any law specifically addressing deepfake technology and this technology is relatively new in India and has not had major consequences so far. According to a recent research by Nema, with the existing legislation there are various causes of actions that may arise. Such as: "violation of fundamental right to privacy; defamation under penal law, and civil law; criminal punishments for offences including forgery, criminal intimidation, breach of peace, communal disharmony, sedition, etc.; computer related offences under information technology act, 2000 that includes transmission or publication of obscene or sexually explicit images, identity theft, cheating by personation, violation of privacy, etc; or infringement of intellectual property rights like copyrights"(Nema, P., 2021).

The Personal Data Protection Bill 2022, provides regulations for processing and protection of personal data of individuals (The Personal Data Protection Bill, 2022). The Bill establishes

that the processed data should not be misleading and that the state, company or individual in charge of processing personal data is under an obligation to make sure of it and contravention of which is punishable under this Bill (The Personal Data Protection Bill, 2022).

The landmark case of Justice KS Puttaswamy (Retd.) v Union of India primarily challenged the Aadhaar scheme in 2006 on the ground that it violates the fundamental rights of the citizens of India. The judgement established that “the right to privacy is protected as an intrinsic part of the right to life and personal liberty under Article 21 and as a part of the freedoms guaranteed by Part III of the Constitution” (Justice K.S. Puttaswamy (Retd.) & Anr. Vs. Union of India & Ors., 2018). Taking the reference from Puttaswamy’s judgement, in Indian Hotel And Restaurant vs The State Of Maharashtra Home on 17 January, 2019, the Supreme Court of India held that the CCTV footage is a personal information and established that “complete surveillance of activities through CCTV cameras inside the premises of dance bars is excessive and disproportionate. The monitoring, recording, storage and retention of dance performances causes unwarranted invasion of privacy and would even subject women bar dancers to threat and blackmail” (Indian Hotel And Restaurant (AHAR) vs The State Of Maharashtra Home, 2019).

According to The Information Technology Act 2000, publishing or transmitting material containing sexually explicit acts, in electronic form is punishable (IT Act, 2000). Section 500 of the Indian Penal Code 1860 establishes that defamation is punishable. According to an online article, the provisions provided by the Indian Penal Code are insufficient to tackle various forms in which deepfakes exist (Deepfakes in India: Regulation and Privacy, 2020). Additionally, Section 66D of the Information Technology Act, 2000 has a provision for when a communication device or computer resource is used with malicious intention, the person can be penalised with imprisonment or can be fined (Das, N., 2022).

Lately, in India the discussion lately has been focused on the impact of deepfakes on politics and their potential to undermine democratic processes and the increasing attacks against the Government established by law. The act of sedition is addressed in Section 124 of Indian Penal Code which establishes that “Whoever by words, either spoken or written, or by signs, or by visible representation, or otherwise, brings or attempts to bring into hatred or contempt, or excites or attempts to excite disaffection towards, the Government established by law in India, shall be punished with imprisonment for life, to which fine may be added, or with imprisonment which may extend to three years, to which fine may be added, or with fine” (IPC Section 124A - Sedition, n.d.).

Existing laws in India do not cover the deepfakes resurrecting a deceased person. There are no provisions relating to the protection of data of deceased persons. But, according to a recent study by the European Parliament, protection of the image of the deceased has been discussed in the data protection law (Tackling deepfakes in European policy, 2022).

Although the existing laws address personal data protection, non-consensual pornography, provide guidance for data processing by state, organisations and individuals, it is still challenging for individuals to opt legal route as the existing legal and platform policies do not address the potential harm caused by deepfake technology in particular.

Policy Recommendations

According to Nema, P. “One of the true dangers of deep fakes lies in the inability of creators to predict how people will react to them and what kind of consequences they might have on the wider society” (2021). With the proliferation of deepfake technology, significant policy intervention will be required to ensure that the technology does not have a negative impact on the society at large. The policy brief discusses various options to minimise the negative impacts of deepfake in India.

Based on the recommendations from the study conducted by the European Parliament, ‘Tackling deepfakes in European policy’, this policy brief discusses the various policy recommendations to address deepfake technology in India (2022).

1. **Creating legal obligations for Deepfake technology-providers and establishing labelling and take-down procedures:** In her work ‘Behind the Screen’, Sarah T. Roberts has suggested that the work of content moderators should be valued and supported by platform companies as one of many necessary steps to build a community that fosters pro-social values that go beyond profit motives (Roberts, 2021). Due to the absence of regulatory measures addressing deepfakes in India, organisations and technology providers are not under any obligation to label deepfake contents. Although the government has banned certain video sharing applications such as tik-tok, there are other platforms such as Instagram and YouTube which should be encouraged to more meaningfully address the fallout. According to an online article, smart-algorithms can be used to remove sophisticated watermarks or meta-data markers simply by being re-encoded for distribution on Instagram or YouTube (TechCrunch Is Part of the Yahoo Family of Brands, 2019). Hence, it becomes imperative that tech companies adopt mechanisms to discourage creation and dissemination of synthetically generated audio-video fragments and aim to foster digital citizenship by developing prosocial terms of service for taking down and labelling nefarious content (Citron & Norton, 2011). The technology platforms should be urged to label the detected deepfake contents or take down the content once notified by the victim by following established procedures (Tackling deepfakes in European policy, 2022).
2. **Ban deepfake political advertising and communication:** Deepfake content in politics has been a focus of discussion lately especially targeting the democratic process and with an increased cyber attacks on the Government established by law in India. Spreading mis-information through manufactured audio-video fragments can potentially lead to geopolitical tensions between countries, internal conflicts and exacerbating religious conflicts in a religion-sensitive countries like India. Although the act of sedition is punishable according to Section 124 of Indian Penal Code, there are no laws pertinent to and addressing deepfake content. Also, research suggests that deepfakes in political campaigning can be used to manipulate political opinions (Tackling deepfakes in European policy, 2022). The highly manipulative effect of deepfake content was witnessed in the recent General Assembly elections in Delhi (2020) where a morphed video of a political candidate bad-mouthing his opponent

surfaced on the internet. Hence, it is imperative to consider a complete ban on deepfake content in political advertising and campaigning.

3. **Post-mortem privacy - Protect personal data of deceased persons:** Proliferation of manipulated images and deepfake technology has made resurrection of deceased persons possible. But, their photos and videos can be used after their death and without their consent which raises questions about fundamental rights and ethics. The study by the European Parliament (Tackling deepfakes in European policy), suggests that there should be provisions made for people to choose on how their data can be used after their death, similar to organ donor codicil (2022). This provision is important especially for eminent personalities whose audios and videos can be easily used for nefarious purposes. In such cases, an online article titled ‘Deepfakes in India: Regulation and Privacy’ by Simran Jain and Piyush Jha suggests that the heirs of the deceased person should be given the right to file a suit similar to the Spanish Data Protection Act and the Privacy Act of Hungary (Deepfakes in India: Regulation and Privacy, 2020).
4. **Ban non-consensual pornography:** Non-consensual pornography has a cascading effect on individuals and at societal level. Deepfake porn is considered to be the most violent form of deepfake videos (Tackling deepfakes in European policy, 2022). The current laws provide guidelines to the victims to claim rights but the legal roadmap for the victims remains unclear. The study by the European Parliament posits that, though the victim’s rights are protected under law, it is often observed that victims are not in a strong position to do anything about it (Tackling deepfakes in European policy, 2022). Hence it is pertinent for policy-makers to consider implementing a complete ban on non-consensual pornography.

References

All's Clear for Deepfakes? Think Again. (n.d.). UC Berkeley School of Information.

<https://www.ischool.berkeley.edu/news/2020/all-clear-deepfakes-think-again>

Ajder, H. et al., (2019, September). The State of Deepfakes: Landscape, Threats, and Impact

https://regmedia.co.uk/2019/10/08/deepfake_report.pdf

Castro, D. (2021, July 16). Deepfakes Are on the Rise — How Should Government Respond? GovTech.

<https://www.govtech.com/policy/deepfakes-are-on-the-rise-how-should-government-respond.html>

Citron, D. K., & Norton, H. (2011). Intermediaries and Hate Speech: Fostering Digital Citizenship for our Information Age. *Boston University Law Review*, 91(4), 1435–1484.

Data Protection Framework | Ministry of Electronics and Information Technology, Government of India. (n.d.).

<https://www.meity.gov.in/data-protection-framework>

Das. (2022, May). What Is Deep Fake Cyber Crime? What Does Indian Law Say About it? Outlook India.

<https://www.outlookindia.com/business/what-is-a-deep-fake-cyber-crime-what-does-indian-law-say-about-it--news-196761>

de Ruiter, A. (2021). The Distinct Wrong of Deepfakes. *Philosophy & Technology*, 34(4), 1311–1332.

<https://doi.org/10.1007/s13347-021-00459-2>

Deepfakes in India: Regulation and Privacy. (2020, May 21). South Asia@LSE.

<https://blogs.lse.ac.uk/southasia/2020/05/21/deepfakes-in-india-regulation-and-privacy/>

Garg, R. (2021, November 12). Is Indian law equipped enough to deal with deepfakes. iLeaders.

<https://blog.ipleaders.in/is-the-indian-law-equipped-enough-to-deal-with-deepfakes/>

General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) – Official Legal Text. (2022, September 27). General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR).

<https://gdpr-info.eu/>

- Huijstee, M. et al. (2022, December). Tackling deepfakes in European policy | Panel for the Future of Science and Technology (STOA) | European Parliament.
[https://www.europarl.europa.eu/stoa/en/document/EPRS_STU\(2021\)690039](https://www.europarl.europa.eu/stoa/en/document/EPRS_STU(2021)690039)
- Hewage, C. (2020, July 17). *Data Protection in the Wake of Deepfakes*. Infosecurity Magazine.
<https://www.infosecurity-magazine.com/next-gen-infosec/data-protection-wake-deepfakes/>
- H.R.3230 – 116th Congress (2019-2020): DEEP FAKES Accountability Act (2019, December 6)
<https://www.congress.gov/bill/116th-congress/house-bill/3230>
- IPC Section 124A - Sedition. (n.d.). A Lawyers Reference.
<https://devgan.in/ipc/section/124A/>
- Indian Hotel And Restaurant(AHAR) vs The State Of Maharashtra Home (2019)
<https://indiankanoon.org/doc/113334597/>
- Jilsblognujs, V. A. P. B. (2020, July 19). Are Indian Laws Equipped To Deal With Deepfakes? The Journal of Indian Law and Society Blog.
<https://jilsblognujs.wordpress.com/2020/07/19/are-indian-laws-equipped-to-deal-with-deepfakes/>
- Justice K.S. Puttaswamy (Retd.) & Anr. vs. Union of India & Ors. (2018).
<https://privacylibrary.ccgmlud.org/case/justice-ks-puttaswamy-ors-vs-union-of-india-ors>
- Kohl, U. (2022). What post-mortem privacy may teach us about privacy. *Computer Law & Security Review*, 47, 105737.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.clsr.2022.105737>
- Konstantin Pantserev, MUAI in the Political Area: the Case of Deepfakes, in *Experts on the Malicious Use of Artificial Intelligence: Challenges for Political Stability and International Psychological Security*, Report by the International Center for Social and Political Studies and Consulting June 2020, Moscow, 1, 14 (2020)
- Lees, D., Bashford-Rogers, T., & Keppel-Palmer, M. (2021). The digital resurrection of Margaret Thatcher: Creative, technological and legal dilemmas in the use of deepfakes in screen drama. *Convergence*, 27(4), 954–973.
<https://doi.org/10.1177/13548565211030452>
- Maras, M. H., & Alexandrou, A. (2018). Determining authenticity of video evidence in the age of artificial intelligence and in the wake of Deepfake videos. *The International Journal of Evidence & Proof*, 23(3), 255–262.
<https://doi.org/10.1177/1365712718807226>

- Mehra, A. (n.d.-a). *Deepfakes Threaten Politics Like Nothing Else - and Indians Are Pioneers*. The Wire.
<https://thewire.in/tech/deepfake-videos-machine-learning-politics-porn>
- Nandle, R. (2022, November 22). India's Digital Personal Data Protection Bill 2022: Does it overhaul the former PDPB? International Association of Privacy Professionals.
<https://iapp.org/news/a/indias-digital-personal-data-protection-bill-2022-does-it-overhaul-the-former-pdpb/>
- Nema, P. (2021). Understanding copyright issues entailing deepfakes in India. *International Journal of Law and Information Technology*.
<https://doi.org/10.1093/ijlit/eaab007>
- Palermo, J. (2020, February 12). Deepfakes: Why you can't believe everything you see and hear. TED Talks.
https://www.ted.com/talks/joseph_palermo_deepfakes_why_you_can_t_believe_everything_you_see_and_hear
- Paris, B. & Donovan, J. (2019, September 18). Deepfakes and cheap fakes: The manipulation of audio and visual evidence. *Data & Society*. Retrieved June 6, 2021, from
https://datasociety.net/wp-content/uploads/2019/09/DS_Deepfakes_Cheap_FakesFinal-1-1.pdf.
- Pavis, M. (2021). Rebalancing our regulatory response to Deepfakes with performers' rights. *Convergence*, 27(4), 974–998.
<https://doi.org/10.1177/13548565211033418>
- Petty, R. D., & D'Rozario, D. (2009). The use of dead celebrities in advertising and marketing: Balancing interests in the right of publicity. *Journal of Advertising*, 38(4), 37–49.
- Raising the Dead: Understanding Post-Mortem Rights of Publicity. (2022, February 8). International Documentary Association.
<https://www.documentary.org/column/raising-dead-understanding-post-mortem-rights-publicity>
- Tackling deepfakes in European policy | Panel for the Future of Science and Technology (STOA) | European Parliament. (n.d.).
[https://www.europarl.europa.eu/stoa/en/document/EPRS_STU\(2021\)690039](https://www.europarl.europa.eu/stoa/en/document/EPRS_STU(2021)690039)
- TechCrunch is part of the Yahoo family of brands. (2019, June 13).
https://techcrunch.com/2019/06/13/deepfakes-accountability-act-would-impose-unenforceable-rules-but-its-a-start/?guce_referrer=aHR0cHM6Ly93d3cuZ29vZ2xlLmNvbS8
- The Information Technology Act, 2000(India)
<https://eprocure.gov.in/cppp/rulesandprocs/kbadqkdlcswfjdelrquehwuxcfmijmuixngudufgbuubgubfugbububjxcgfvsbdihbfgGhdgFHtyhRtMjk4NzY=>
- THE DIGITAL PERSONAL DATA PROTECTION BILL 2022(India)

https://www.meity.gov.in/writereaddata/files/The%20Digital%20Personal%20Data%20Protection%20Bill%2C%202022_0.pdf

Westerlund, M. (2019). The Emergence of Deepfake Technology: A Review. *Technology Innovation Management Review*, 9(11), 39–52.
<https://doi.org/10.22215/timreview/1282>